

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of a cobalt(II) complex containing a N-donor Schiff base : DNA binding and antimicrobial activity

Dhananjay Dey^a, Biswajit Chowdhury^a, Shampa Dutta^b, Partha Sarathi Sengupta^c, Niranjana Koley^a and Bhaskar Biswas^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Raghunathpur College, Purulia-723 133, West Bengal, India

E-mail : icbbiswas@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Environmental Science, The University of Burdwan, Golapbag, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Vivekananda Mahavidyalaya, Burdwan-713 103, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of a mononuclear cobalt(II) compound, [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**) [L = N-(1-pyridin-2-yl-phenylidene)-N'-[2-(2-[(1-pyridin-2-ylphenylidene)amino]ethyl)amino]ethyl]ethane-1,2-diamine] (**1**) is reported. The ligand and cobalt(II) complex were characterized by elemental analysis, FTIR, UV-Vis spectroscopy, ¹H NMR, electron spray ionization (ESI) mass spectrometry and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) studies. PXRD studies revealed that **1** crystallizes in P-1 space group with *a* = 12.5032(3) Å, *b* = 12.4013(3) Å and *c* = 13.162(4) Å with unit cell volume is 1617.420 (Å)³. The binding property of the complex with DNA has been investigated using absorption and emission studies. Spectroscopic investigations revealed an intercalative binding mode of **1** with CT-DNA. The activity data show that the cobalt(II) complex has effectively screened bacterial and fungal activity. Structural parameters of the L and **1** has been computed using Density Function Theory (DFT) to understand the molecular geometries of the ligand and its cobalt(II) complex.

Keywords : Cobalt(II) complex, Schiff base, Density Function Theory, DNA binding, antimicrobial study.

Introduction

Searching for a new material associated with various diseases has long been an issue for the purpose of research. In particular, the discovery of effective anti-cancer, antibacterial and antifungal agents made this an appealing research field¹⁻⁷. Thus design and synthesis of small coordination systems that can recognize specific sites of DNA through formation of non-covalently associated complexation is a fundamental requirement, not only for gaining insight into the reactive models for protein-nucleic acid interactions and probes of DNA structure, but also for obtaining information about drug design and tools of molecular biology⁸⁻¹¹. Cobalt is an essential trace element found in cobalamin and a few other metalloproteins¹². Cobalamin is necessary for the formation of myelin, an insulating layer found around nerves, in the support of red blood cell production, for the metabolism of fats and carbohydrates, and in the synthesis

of proteins¹². Schiff bases, named after Hugo Schiff (1834-1915), are a significant class of compounds which can be used in a variety of studies, such as organic synthesis, catalyst and drug design and models for active sites of metalloenzymes. The application of octahedral complexes has permitted the targeting of specific DNA sites by matching the shape, symmetry and functionality of the metal complex to that of the DNA target. Cobalt complexes containing Schiff base ligands are of great interest since they exhibit numerous biological activities such as anti-tumor, anticandida (Saha *et al.*, 2004), antimicrobial activities, etc.¹³⁻¹⁵. We have been interested in designing metal complex molecules which can specifically interact with DNA. In this direction, we have synthesized and characterized a new Co^{II} complex, [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ (**1**) [L = N-(1-pyridin-2-yl-phenylidene)-N'-[2-(2-[(1-pyridin-2-ylphenylidene)amino]ethyl)amino]ethyl]ethane-1,2-diamine] whose binding ability with Calf Thymus-DNA

(CT-DNA) is investigated by spectrophotometry and spectrofluorimetry. It effectively screens the bacterial and fungal activity. Investigation of molecular simulation studies using density functional theory (DFT) of the ligand and its cobalt(II) compound helps to understand the molecular geometries in a better way.

Results and discussion

Synthesis of N-(1-pyridin-2-yl-phenylidene)-N'-[2-[(1-pyridin-2ylphenylidene)amino]ethyl]amino]ethane-1,2-diamine (L) and its cobalt(II) complex (1) :

The hexadentate Schiff base ligand (L) was synthesized by 1 : 2 condensation of triethylenetetramine and 2-benzoylpyridine in dehydrated alcohol. The cobalt(II) complex, **1** was prepared using reaction between hydrated cobalt(II) perchlorate salt and the ligand in methanol (Scheme 1).

Spectroscopic characterization :

The coordination sites of the Schiff base ligand involved in coordination with the metal ion has been examined by careful comparison of the IR spectra of the free ligand and complex. The IR spectrum of the free ligand is characterized mainly by the strong peaks at 1618 and 1595 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the stretching frequencies of C=N (imine). Sharp peak raised at 3283 cm^{-1} is due to presence of aliphatic secondary amine (-N-H). In

IR spectrum of **1**, the well resolved peaks at 1608 and 1588 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1) is due to C=N stretch¹⁶. **1** shows peaks at 1092 and 625 cm^{-1} due to symmetrical asymmetrical stretch of ClO_4^- and weak bands in the range 2980–2900 cm^{-1} are due to the aliphatic C-H stretching frequency.

The electronic spectra provided good information regarding the arrangements of the ligands around the metal ions. The UV-Vis spectrum for ligand in methanolic medium exhibits two high intensity band in the UV region (238 and 272 nm) which are assignable to $\pi-\pi^*$ to $n-\pi^*$ transitions and Co^{II} complex shows high intensity transitions in the range of 200 to 600 nm. The UV-Vis spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ exhibits two regions : three absorption bands in the UV region (239, 298, 241 nm) corresponding to the intraligand and ligand-to-metal transitions of L and a second range from about 525 to 575 nm (Fig. 2). The latter band originates from the same $d-d$ transitions. The mass spectral analysis of the Co^{II} complex is recorded in methanol solution and it is in good agreement with the theoretical molecular mass of the complex. This mass spectral study of this Co^{II} complex confirms the mononuclear nature of the Co^{II} complex. The presence of molecular ion $\{[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2\} + \text{H}^+$ peak at m/z 733.58 (Calcd. 733.099) in the spectrum consolidates the proposed structure.

Scheme 1. Synthetic procedure of ligand and cobalt(II) complex.

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**).

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of L and (**1**).

Structure determination :

PXRD characterization :

All the peaks in the powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ can be indexed with the triclinic structure with *P*-1 space group using WINPLOTR programme. The extracting cell parameters are $a = 12.5032(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 12.4013(3) \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 13.162(4) \text{ \AA}$ with unit cell volume is $1617.420 (\text{ \AA})^3$. From PXRD, it is revealed that the complex is in crystalline phase.

Molecular geometry :

Crystalline compounds of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ were ob-

tained directly during the synthesis. According to the PXRD data, the mononuclear complex crystallizes in the triclinic space group *P*-1. The proposed molecular structure of **1** in Scheme 1 and our previous experiences¹⁷⁻¹⁹ signifies the octahedral geometry of the Co^{II} complex in solid state. Structural characterizations using different spectroscopic probes confirm the octahedral coordination geometry of **1**. The Co^{II} centre in **1** is best described as a distorted octahedron with six nitrogen atoms coordination from ligand unit. Among the six neutral donor sites, two N centers donate their lone pairs to cobalt from pyridine-N, two from imine-N and two linkages are from

lone pairs of amine-N. The charge balance is occurred by two anionic perchlorate moieties and suggests cobalt atom in the metal complex is in +2 oxidation state.

DFT study :

Though we have isolated the compound in polycrystalline phase but failed to produce single crystals instead of repeated reactions in different solvent mixture and conditions, we tried to assess the observed data at molecular level with the help of molecular modeling in DFT technique. Molecular modeling had been successfully used to detect three dimensional arrangements of atoms in complexes by means of semi-empirical molecular orbital calculations at the B3LYP level using 6-31G(d,p) basis set provided by the Gaussian 09 suite. Their utilization in the demonstration of molecular structure and structural properties data of the studied ligand and its complexes conducted with calculated HOMO and LUMO energies, selected bond lengths and bond angles of the free ligand and its complexes are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The optimized structure of the cobalt(II) complex is shown in Fig. 3. In the gas phase, the big hexadentate N-donor Schiff base ligand (L) shows a cage like structure while the cobalt(II) complex in its optimized structure exhibits penta-coordinated geometry, remaining one nitrogen centre uncoordinated to metal centre. During coordination of the six nitrogen donor sites to cobalt(II) centre, a high steric strain from ligand unit weakens one of the secondary amine-N coordination axially and the Co^{II} centre

doesn't allow -NH group to coordinate. Hence, Co^{II} complex **1** remains penta-coordinated with one axially elongated uncoordinated secondary -NH unit. The structure of **1** seems to be a distorted square pyramid in gas phase.

The important geometric parameters of the ligand and its cobalt complex are presented in Table 1. The cobalt-nitrogen bond lengths vary from 1.873 to 2.063 Å and the maximum bond length in **1** is found as 2.063 Å for Co1-N69. The maximum bond angle is found in **1** as N2-Co1-N40 = 164.79° and the minimum bond angle is N47-Co1-N69 = 79.18°.

The difference between HOMO and LUMO is a measure of the reactivity of the compound. According to the electronic behavior, HOMO acts as electron donor and LUMO acts as electron acceptor. The calculated energy gap between HOMO and LUMO in ligand and its Co^{II} complex is 0.12 a.u. and 0.063 a.u. respectively (Figs. 4 and 5). The larger the HOMO/LUMO energy gap (LUMO-HOMO), the more stable/less reactive the molecule^{20,21} is and thus result shows complex (**1**) is less stable and more reactive than its corresponding ligand (L).

DNA binding studies :

Spectrophotometric titration :

Electronic absorption spectroscopy is an effective method to determine the binding mode of metal complex with DNA. To examine the binding mode of [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ with DNA, the UV-Vis spectra of the

Table 1. Theoretically calculated bond lengths (Å) for the cobalt(II) complex

Types of bond	Bond length (Å)	Types of bond	Bond length (Å)	Types of bond	Bond length (Å)
Co1-N2	2.028	Co1-N69	2.063	N40-C31	1.348
Co1-N3	3.824	N2-C8	1.478	N40-C32	1.389
Co1-N12	1.873	N2-C15	1.483	N47-C48	1.354
Co1-N40	1.924	N12-C19	1.357	N69-C61	1.386
Co1-N47	1.999	N12-C13	1.450	N69-C62	1.342

Table 2. Theoretical bond angles (°) for the cobalt(II) complex

Bond angle (°)	Bond angle (°)	Bond angle (°)	Bond angle (°)		
N2-Co1-N12	83.27	N12-Co1-N47	145.31	Co1-O4-C36	127.41
N2-Co1-N40	164.79	N12-Co1-N69	135.46	Co1-O5-C10	127.41
N2-Co1-N47	94.39	N40-Co1-N69	96.06	Co1-O2-C13	129.19
N2-Co1-N69	98.37	N40-Co1-N69	94.41	Co1-O3-C32	129.19
N12-Co1-N40	81.84	N47-Co1-N69	79.18		

Fig. 3. Optimized geometry of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})]^{2+}$.

Fig. 4. Frontier molecular orbital's contribution in the ground state of ligand.

Fig. 5. Frontier molecular orbital's contribution in the ground state of 1.

complex were recorded during the titration with CT-DNA. The UV-Vis spectrum exhibits a hypochromic effect centred at 269 nm (Fig. 6). In general, the observation of hypochromism is associated with the binding of the metal complex to DNA helix due to the intercalative mode involving a strong stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore of the complex and the base pairs of DNA²². This result can be rationally explained as follows: π^* -orbitals of the intercalated ligands are coupled with the π -orbitals of the base pairs when $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ intercalates the base pairs of CT-DNA. The coupled orbitals are partially filled by electrons, which gives rise to the decrease of the π - π^* transition energy and of the transition probabilities, and, as a result, exhibits hypochromism²³. The binding constant, K_b , for $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ has been determined from the plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ and found to be $5.18(0.2) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.95472$ for four points) (Fig. 6).

Spectrofluorimetric titration :

Ethidium bromide (EB) can emit intense fluorescence in the presence of DNA due to the strong intercalation between the adjacent DNA base pairs. The fluorescent light of the EB-DNA system can be quenched by addition of the second agent, since it interacts with DNA and replaces the EB molecules. The quenching degree of fluorescence for the EB-DNA system is usually used to determine the binding extent of the agent and DNA²⁴. Addition of $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ to DNA pretreated with EB causes an appreciable reduction in the fluorescence intensity (Fig. 7), indicating that the complex competes with EB to bind with DNA. The reduction of the emission intensity gives a measure of the DNA binding propensity of the complex and stacking interaction (intercalation) between adjacent DNA base pairs. Here, for $[\text{Co}(\text{L})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$, a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA at 620–628 nm was observed by increasing the

Fig. 6. UV-Vis spectra of [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ during the titration with CT-DNA in the tris-HCl buffer. The increase of DNA concentration is indicated by an arrow; Linear plot of [DNA]/(ε_a - ε_f) vs [DNA] for the titration of CT-DNA with [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ in the tris-HCl buffer (binding constant $K_b = 5.18(0.2) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$; $R = 0.9547$ for four points).

Fig. 7. (a) Emission spectra of the CT-DNA-EB system in the tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 522 \text{ nm}$). The increase of the complex concentration is indicated by an arrow. (b) Plot of I_0/I vs [complex] for the titration of the CT-DNA-EB system with [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ (the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant $K_{\text{sv}} = 2.4(0.1) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$; $R = 0.9979$ for four points).

concentration of the complex (Fig. 7). The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the complex is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I vs [complex] (Fig. 7), the K_{sv} value for [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ was found to be $2.4(0.1) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9979$ for four points), indicating a strong affinity of the complex to CT-DNA.

Bio-assay investigations :

In testing the antibacterial and antifungal activity of

these compounds, we used more than one test organism to increase the chance of detecting antibiotic principles in tested materials. 100 μL of microbial suspension was spread onto agar plates corresponding to the broth in which they were maintained. Isolated colonies of each organism that might be playing a pathogenic role should be selected from primary agar plates and tested for susceptibility by well diffusion method. The metal complex solution in DMSO has been screened for their antimicro-

bial activity and the results are presented in Table 3 and Table 4. The $[\text{Co(L)}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complex showed the maximum antimicrobial activity against the *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Fusarium oxysporum*. The order of minimum antimicrobial activity against the test complex as is follows : *Escherichia coli* > *Klebsiella pneumoniae* > *Proteus vulgaris* > *Cryptococcus neoformans* > *Aspergillus niger*.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of the complex (Well size : 6 mm) at different concentrations/ml

Organisms	25 μg	50 μg	75 μg	100 μg
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	–	–	3 mm	4 mm
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	–	–	1 mm	2 mm
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6 mm	7 mm	8 mm	11 mm
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	3 mm	5 mm	6 mm	7 mm
<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	–	–	–	2 mm

Table 4. Antifungal activity of the complex (Well size : 6 mm) at different concentrations/ml

Organisms	25 μg	50 μg	75 μg	100 μg
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	2 mm	3 mm	4 mm	6 mm
<i>Cryptococcus neoformans</i>	–	–	3 mm	4 mm
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	–	–	1 mm	2 mm

The enhanced activity of the complex over the Schiff base can be explained on the basis of mechanistic aspects of Tweedy's Chelation theory²⁵. The lipid and polysaccharides are some important constituents of cell walls and membranes, which are preferred for metal ion interaction. In addition to this, the cell wall also contains amino phosphates, carbonyl and cysteinyl ligands, which maintain the integrity of the membrane acting as a diffusion barrier and also provides suitable site for bonding. In our case, the cationic cobalt(II) complex probably binds with phosphates or cysteinyl groups of cell wall in the microorganism. This leads to breakdown of the permeability barrier of the cell, resulting in interference with the normal cell process.

On the other hand, due to enhancement of less polar character of this Co^{II} complex, it is probably adsorbed on the surface of the cell wall of microorganisms and disturbs the respiration process of the cell and thus blocks the synthesis of the proteins that restricts further growth of the organisms. So, the Co^{II} -Schiff base complex behaves as the growth-inhibitor for microorganism.

Experimental

Chemicals, solvents and starting materials :

High purity cobalt(II) perchlorate hexahydrate (E. Merck, India), 2-benzoyl pyridine (Aldrich, UK) and triethylenetetraamine (Aldrich, UK) were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. The CT-DNA and ethidium bromide (EB) were obtained from Sigma. All the other reagents and solvents are of analytical grade and were purchased from commercial sources and used as received. **Caution!** Perchlorate salts of metal ions are potentially explosive, especially in the presence of organic ligands. Only a small amount of material should be prepared and it should be handled with care.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, 4000–300 cm^{-1}) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground-state absorption and steady-state fluorescence measurements were made with a Jasco model V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and Hitachi model F-4010 spectrofluorimeter, respectively. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC300 spectrometer. The crystalline phase was identified by powder X-ray diffraction patterns (XRD) of the materials by using a BRUKER AXS (Model : 8D-ADVANCE) diffractometer with a $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation source under continuous scanning mode in the range 8° – 60° . Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectrum was recorded using a Q-tof-micro quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Synthesis of L and $[\text{Co(L)}](\text{ClO}_4)_2$:

The Schiff base L was prepared following a reported method^{17–19}. The details are given below :

2-Benzoylpyridine (0.366 g, 2 mmol) was refluxed with triethylenetetraamine (0.146 g, 1 mmol) in dehydrated alcohol (15 ml). After 10 h the reaction solution was evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a gummy mass, which was dried and stored *in vacuo* over CaCl_2 for subsequent use. Yield : 3.820 g (80%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_6$ (L) : C, 75.38; H, 6.74; N, 17.58. Found : C, 74.94; H, 6.51; N, 17.25%; IR (KBr pellet, cm^{-1}) : 3283 (s) (ν_{NH}), 1618 (s), 1595 (s) ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$); UV-Vis [λ_{max} , nm, MeOH] : 238, 272; ^1H NMR (δ ppm, 400 Mz, DMSO-

d_6) δ : 8.810–8.806 (2H, Py-H), 8.148–7.385 (16H, Ar-H), 4.104–4.092 (2H, s), 3.73–2.50 (12H, s) ppm; ESI-MS [m/z , (1+H⁺), MeOH] = 478.92.

A methanolic solution (5 ml) of L (0.476 g, 1 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of Co(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O (0.365 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (10 ml). The violet solution was filtered and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. After about a week the solution produced violet coloured crystalline compound. Yield : 0.2830 g (77% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₂N₆Cl₂O₈Co (1) : C, 49.06; H, 4.39; N, 11.44. Found : C, 49.01; H, 4.30; N, 11.36%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 1616, 1590 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1095, 626 (ν_{ClO_4}); UV-Vis [λ_{max} , nm, MeOH] : 298, 341, 547 nm; ESI-MS [m/z (1+H⁺), MeOH] = 733.58 (molecular ion peak).

DNA binding experiments :

All experiments involving CT-DNA were performed in the tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane hydrochloride (tris-HCl) buffer solution. Stock solution of DNA was stored at 4 °C. The buffer solution of CT-DNA gave a ratio value of UV absorbance at 260 and 280 nm of about 1.9, indicating that DNA was sufficiently independent of protein²². The concentration of CT-DNA per nucleotide was determined by UV-Vis spectroscopy using the absorption coefficient (6600 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) at 260 nm²². The solution of [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ was prepared by dissolving the complex in dimethyl formamide and diluted with the tris-HCl buffer (5 mM, pH 7.2, 50 mM NaCl) to required concentrations for all experiments. The UV-Vis spectra were recorded after each successive addition of DNA and equilibration (10 min). From the observed data, the intrinsic binding constant K_b was calculated by using the following equation²³ :

$$[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f) = [DNA]/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f) + (\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)/K_b,$$

where ϵ_a , ϵ_f , ϵ_b are the apparent, free and bound compound extinction coefficients, respectively. A plot of [DNA]/($\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f$) vs [DNA] gave a slope of $1/(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_f)$ and the “y” intercept is equal to $(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)/K_b$, where K_b is the ratio of the slope to the “y” intercept. The background correction was done in the absorption titration by keeping the same concentration of DNA in the reference cell.

Ethidium bromide (EB) fluorescence displacement experiments were also performed in order to investigate

the interaction mode of [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂. EB has been used to probe the interaction of the complexes with DNA. The EB fluorescence intensity is enhanced in the presence of DNA because of its intercalation into the helix and it is quenched by the addition of another molecule that displaces the EB from DNA²⁴. Herein a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA at 620–628 nm was recorded by increasing the concentration of the complex. The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the [Co(L)](ClO₄)₂ is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv}[\text{complex}],$$

where I_0 and I are the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of a quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [complex] is the concentration of the quencher.

In vitro antimicrobial activity :

All the bacterial strains and fungal strains were sourced from ATCC as *Escherichia coli* 8739TM, *Staphylococcus aureus* 6538TM, *Salmonella typhi* 14028TM, *Proteus vulgaris* 8427TM, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 700721TM and *Cryptococcus neoformans* MYA-565TM, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus niger* 16404TM. Antibacterial activity of the ligand and the complex were tested against the bacterial species by well diffusion method²⁶. The ligand and complex were also tested against the fungal species cultured on sabouraud dextrose agar medium by the well diffusion method. The bacteria test organisms were grown on muller hinton agar and the fungal species on sabouraud dextrose agar in petri plates. The pathogens were swabbed uniformly onto the individual plates using sterile cotton swabs. Using gel puncture, wells of 6 mm diameter were made. Different concentration (25 μ g, 50 μ g, 75 μ g and 100 μ g) of test sample was poured onto each well on all plates. After incubation at 37 °C for 24 h for bacteria and 28 °C for 72 h for fungi, the different levels of zone of inhibition were measured excluding the diameter of agar well.

Computational details :

Full unconstrained geometry optimization for the Schiff base ligand and its cobalt(II) complex and frequency calculation have been carried out at the Density Functional methods. These are three parameter fit non-local correlation provided by widely used gradient corrected corre-

lated functional of Lee, Yang and Parr (LYP) expression and exchange functional suggested by Becke^{27,28}. All minimized geometries were checked by frequency calculations to be true minima. The basis set used in the present work is 6-31g(d)^{29,30}. All the electronic structures calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 programme³¹. Thermal contribution of the energetic properties was calculated at 298 K and 1 atmosphere.

Conclusions

In summary, we have synthesized and spectroscopically characterized an octahedral cobalt(II) complex containing neutral hexadentate N-donor schiff base (L) complex. The binding constant for the complex is found to be $5.18 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9547$ for four points). The linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant was determined as 2.4×10^4 ($R = 0.9979$ for four points). Overall studies indicate an intercalative mode of binding with the CT-DNA. The biological activities of the Schiff base and the cobalt(II) complex against bacterial and fungal organisms are promising and need further investigation on different species. The structures of the ligand and its Co^{II} complex were geometrically optimized and their structural parameters were calculated at the B3LYP level using 6-31G(d,p) basis set.

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